

Contribution of Dr. Indumati Naik in Indian Freedom Struggle

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Introduction

Dr. Indumati Naik was a significant figure in the Indian freedom struggle, particularly known for her contribution in the fields of education, social reform, and women's empowerment.

Dr. Indumati Naik was deeply involved in promoting education among women, recognizing it as a vital tool for empowerment. Dr. Naik worked relentlessly to establish schools and educational institutions for girls, aiming to break the societal barriers that restricted women's access to education.

Her efforts extended to social reforms, where she actively campaigned against prevalent social issues like child marriage, caste discrimination, and the mistreatment of widows. Dr. Naik worked towards creating awareness and initiating reforms to uplift the status of marginalized communities, especially women.

Dr. Indumati Naik was also involved in the Indian freedom movement. She participated in various non-violent protests, rallies, and movements against British rule in India. Her advocacy for freedom and social justice was integral in mobilizing communities and garnering support for the cause of independence.

As a feminist and social activist, Dr. Naik played a pivotal role in empowering women. She encouraged women to participate actively in the freedom struggle and emphasized the importance of their involvement in shaping the future of the nation.

While specific details about her contributions might vary, Dr. Indumati Naik's legacy primarily revolves around her dedication to education, social reform, and women's empowerment during the pivotal period of India's struggle for independence. Her efforts helped lay the groundwork for a more inclusive and equitable society in post-independent India.

The contribution of Dr. Indumati Naik to the nation's independence is the subject of this paper. Nearly every region of the nation saw women join in the struggle for independence; historians have mostly ignored the political awakening among women, while discussions of political consciousness among men have been extensively covered. Without a doubt, the different regions gave the national movement both male and female leadership. In this article the role of various women Dr. Annie Beasant, Sarojini Naidu, Avantika Bai Gokhale, Sarala Debi Ghosal, Sarojini Naidu, Basanti Devi, Kasturba Gandhi, Meera Ben, Dr. Sushila Nayar and many more have been presented who take part in different movements launched for the independence of India.

Mahatma Gandhi's introduction to Indian politics in 1917 marked the beginning of a new chapter in the history of women's struggle. He argued that women were more capable of self-sacrifice and endurance, less self-seeking, and more morally courageous than men when it came to engaging in nonviolent passive resistance. Gandhi knew that women could be passive resisters because of his experience in South Africa. In India, he experimented with his instrument of Satyagraha and found that women might be useful activists. Dr. Indumati Naik has been a rich and varied career in medicine, social work and politics.

Family background

Indumati was born in 08th August 1897 at Pune, Maharashtra She was born in a brahmin family, her father's name was Narayan Veerkar. She completed her primary education from Hujurpaga School, Pune; she was the topper in the school. She married to Dr. Ramchandra Naik from Belgaum in 1913. She tried her best to become a good doctor and scored good marks in almost all & stood first in LCPS exam in Medicine & Surgery in the year of 1921. British offered a job but refused to join at Sasoon Hospital in Poona.

Participation in Mulshi Satyagraha

This movement, popularly known as the Mulshi satyagraha (insistence on truth), was spearheaded in the early 1920s by Pandurang Mahadev (Senapati) Bapat and V.M. Bhuskute and extended beyond Pune and the 52 submergence villages of the dam. What makes this fight from a century ago significant is that many women took part in it and were imprisoned. July 1920 – Public meeting of Mahatma Gandhi inspired Indumati Naik to participate in Mulshi Satyagraha against the dispossession of farmers by a Dam project. Dr. Indumati Naik was unanimously elected as President of Women Satyagraha. In her speech she said, prime duty of every women is to give support to our men in the Satyagraha like Seeta.

Participation in Non-Cooperation Movement in Princely state Bhor Maharashtra

In July & November 1921 decided to start Non-Cooperation Movement in Princely state Bhor Maharashtra against the rule of oppression. Dr. Indumati Naik toured the princely state and delivered lecture on Swarajya, Swadeshi & Satyagraha. The English newspaper “Janmbhoomi” published a headline that Non-Cooperation Movement by a Woman Dr. Indumati Naik.

Contribution to the Constructive programme in Non-Cooperation Movement

In 1920 Poona Spinning Committee was established in Poona. Dr. Indumati Naik was secretary of Poona Spinning Committee. She started the spinning class for women. Till the end of her life Khadi was the mission of her life.

Swadeshi Bangle Shop

Dr. Indumati Naik started swadeshi bangle shop at her house. Using swadeshi bangle was a sign of patriotism. Women would come her home to purchase bangles and she was able to tell them about swadeshi and Swarajya. She was appointed as Member of AICC from Poona in 1921 & appointed to the Executive Committee of the Congress Committee. Sarojini Naidu, Kasturba, Vijayalakshmi Nehru (later Pandit) Swarupa Rani and Dr. Indumati Naik were the only five members of the executive committee. They were called 'Panchkanya Committee'.

Promoted national education among women

For this, a national girl's school was established in Belgaum. He started the weekly 'Lok Paksh' in Belgaum in December 1923 as the mouthpiece of the Congress. The aim of this weekly was to convey the thoughts of Congress program, criticism of the government's guilty program, women's issues, Hindu-Muslim issues etc. to the people.

Other Works

In 1924, Gandhiji was ill by the appendix. At that time he was brought from prison to Sassoon. Dr. Dr. Modak, who was proficient in surgery while operating on Gandhiji. Indumati was called to his aid. Dr. Indumati Naik also participated in Quit India movement 1942.

Conclusion

It has been concluded that women played a crucial role in India's independence. These women made sacrifices during the independence movement that were equally great to those of the males who were shot by police.

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